

Review of Wing Morphology in Fossil and Modern Species of Humpbacked Flies (Diptera: Phoridae)

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Appendix 2 - Complementary Figures of Phoridae

Figure S2.1. **Photographs of wings of living specimens with a early model.** *Archisciada* sp., LACM no number: a) full wing, b) zoom of basal part, c) *Sciadocera* sp., male, LACM no number

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Figure S2.2. **Photographs of wings of Living specimens with a recent model.** a) *Dohrniphora* sp., LACM No number, b) *Conicera* sp., LACM No number, c) *Metopina* sp., LACM No number, d) *Chronocephalus* sp., LACM No number.

Figure S2.3. *Agaphora iunior* Mostovski, 1999.

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Figure S2.4. **Photographs of wings of fossil specimens with a early model.** a) *Prioriphora* sp. SMF-Be 2381.2 in Burmese amber, b) potentiel *Ulrichophora* sp. CCHH 4804-3 (LACM) in Baltic amber.

Figure S2.5. **Photographs of wings of fossil and extant specimens with a recent model.** a) Potential *Aenigmatias* sp. CCHH 1804-1 (LACM), in Baltic amber, b–c) *Gymnophora* sp., MNHN no number, living species, full wing and zoom of proximal part, respectively.

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Figure S2.6. **Hypothesis of reduction of Phoridae medial veins.** a) Early wing, M₁ and M₂ are clearly separate from RP, and M₁ is connected to M₂ or reduced proximally ①, and all three proximal cells are present, b) Recent wing, RP fork reduced ②, M₁ and M₂ migrated to the posterior radial system without fused to RP veins ③. Opening of the proximal cells and a change in their orientation from posteriorly curved to sigmoidal ④, c) Wing with an "extreme" reduction of venation, proximal reduction of M₁ and M₂ ④, M₄ extending proximally ⑤, disappearance of the proximal cells, and M₁ and M₂ change in their orientation from sigmoidal to anteriorly curved.

Figure S2.7. **Wing patterns.** a) Lonchopteridae, b) Opetiidae, c) Platypetizidae, d) Ironomyiidae.